

Two New Methods of Synthesis of Norpinic Acid.

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A number of unsuccessful attempts (Ganguli, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1922, 5, 23; Clemo and Welch, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2621) have been made to achieve the synthesis of norpinic acid to which Bayer assigned the formula (I).

Kerr (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 614) has, however, finally succeeded in achieving this synthesis by the condensation of the sodium derivative of Gaureschi imide with methylene iodide, and by hydrolysing the bridged imide thus formed into the cyano acid (II) and finally into *trans*-norpinic acid (I). Shoppee and Simonsen (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1929, 48, 730) converted this into *cis*-norpinic anhydride and the *cis*-acid, and established its identity with the acid obtained from *dl*-pinonic acid. As Kerr's method is round about and when repeated in this laboratory was found not to give the yield described by the author, it seemed desirable to try the synthesis of this acid by the condensation of sodium methylenedimalonic ester and $\beta\beta$ -dichloropropane. It is to be mentioned here that though this scheme is not much different from the unsuccessful scheme of Clemo and Welch (*loc. cit.*), the success achieved in these experiments is primarily due to the application of a convenient method* discovered by one of us (P. C. G.), *viz.*, of bringing about the condensation of alkylenedihalides with suitable disodium

* This method has already been found to be of general applicability and has been adopted for the synthesis of ethyl keto-pinane dicarboxylate by the action of trimethylene bromide upon the disodium derivative of ketonorpinic ester, also in bridging succinosuccinic ester *via* its disodium derivative by means of methylene iodide, etc. (*cf. Current Science*, 1933, 2, 53).

derivative of compounds in benzene suspension by prolonged heating in a sealed vessel at a high temperature, thus leading to the formation of ring-closed compounds. The tetracarboxylic ester (III),

obtained by the action of methylene iodide and $\beta\beta$ -dichloropropane respectively upon the disodium derivatives of isopropylidenedimalonic ester and methylenedimalonic ester has yielded norpinic acid on hydrolysis and decarboxylation according to the following scheme :

As the result of a large number of experiments conducted under varying conditions it has been possible to effect considerable improvement upon the method of preparation of isopropylidenemalonic and dimalonic esters described by Clemo and Welch.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of isopropylidenemalonic ester.—A mixture of ethyl malonate (1170 g.), acetic anhydride (1080 g.) and a solution of anhydrous zinc chloride (90 g.) in acetone (990 g.) was heated in three round-bottomed flasks under reflux over free flames, so adjusted that the mixture did not boil very vigorously in the beginning. All possible precautions were taken to avoid contact with moisture. The

reaction mixture after 100 hours' continuous heating was poured into an equal volume of water, thoroughly shaken and then allowed to stand for 24 hours during which the unchanged acetic anhydride was converted into acetic acid. The ester layer was then separated and thoroughly washed with water. The ether extract of the aqueous washings was mixed with the ester and washed with sodium carbonate solution. After drying over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and removal of ether, the residue was repeatedly fractionated and the portion distilling at 116-120°/14 mm. collected, yield 1315 g. Clemo and Welch obtained 810 g. from 1170 g. of malonic ester.

Preparation of isopropylidenedimalonic ester.—*iso*Propylidenemalonic ester (80 g.) was heated in an autoclave in mixture of absolute alcohol and anhydrous benzene (1:1) with an equivalent of sodiomalonic ester for 48 hours at 160° at 100 lbs. pressure. The solid residue obtained after the removal of alcohol and benzene was dissolved in the minimum quantity of cold water, acidified with dilute sulphuric acid in the cold and the separated oil extracted with ether, dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate, ether removed and the residual oily product repeatedly fractionated. The portion distilling at 170-172°/3 mm. was collected, yield 42 g. It was identified to be isopropylidenedimalonic ester by hydrolysis to $\beta\beta$ -dimethylglutaric acid.

Action of $\beta\beta$ -dichloropropane upon the sodium derivative of methylenedimalonic ester. Isolation of 2:2-dimethylcyclobutane-1:1:3:3-tetracarboxylic acid.—Methylenedimalonic ester (44 g.), prepared according to the method of Knoevenagel (*Ber.*, 1894, 27, 2346) and thoroughly purified by repeated fractional distillation, was converted into its sodium derivative by heating under reflux with sodium (5 g.) in anhydrous benzene suspension for 8 hours. Most of the benzene was removed in *vacuo* and the residual jelly like mass heated with $\beta\beta$ -dichloropropane (15 g.) in a closed soda-water bottle for 30 hours in an oil-bath at 140° when sodium iodide settled at the bottom and the liquid appeared brown in colour and was quite mobile. To remove any unreacted methylenedimalonic ester, the reaction mixture was heated under reflux with sodium wire. The filtered solution was freed from benzene and the viscous brown oil subjected to fractional distillation at 4 mm. pressure; about half of the liquid distilled up to 180°. The residual liquid did not distil but showed signs of decomposition on further heating; so the distillation was discontinued at this stage. The contents of the distilling flask (about

10 g.) were kept for hydrolysis with potassium hydroxide (14 g.) in aqueous alcohol (100 c.c.) for 3 days. After removing the alcohol in *vacuo* the residual brown solid was dissolved in cold water and shaken repeatedly with ether. The alkaline solution was then carefully acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid under cooling and extracted with ether repeatedly. The yellow ethereal extract was dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate, ether removed, and the light brown viscous residue kept in a vacuum desiccator when after about a fortnight it solidified. This was crystallised from acetone-benzene mixture being very soluble in the former, m.p. 200°. (Found: C, 45.8; H, 4.9. $C_{10}H_{12}O_8$ requires C, 46.1; H, 4.6 per cent).

Isolation of norpinic acid.—The above tetracarboxylic acid was heated in a liquid paraffin-bath to 220-240° till there was no more evolution of carbon dioxide (tested with lime water). The product was dissolved in water and the solution evaporated to dryness. The thick viscous mass thus obtained was kept in a vacuum desiccator, when it solidified after 24 hours, m.p. 144-45°. The solid was dissolved in water, filtered, concentrated to small bulk on a water-bath and allowed to stand in an ice chamber, when crystals, m.p. 146° (softening at 137°), separated after a week. No rise in the melting point was observed on further two recrystallisations; yield is very poor. (Found: C, 55.62; H, 7.0. $C_8H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 55.8; H, 6.9 per cent).

The decarboxylation was also carried out by heating the tetra-acid under reflux with 50% sulphuric acid for 24 hours when the evolution of carbon dioxide ceased. After addition of water the mass was heated again and filtered. The filtrate was extracted repeatedly with ether. The residue left after removal of ether was purified as above.

Action of methylene iodide upon sodium derivative of isopropylidenedimalonic ester.—The sodium derivative of isopropylidenedimalonic ester, prepared by heating the ester (32 g.) with sodium wire (4.6 g.) in anhydrous benzene solution, was heated with methylene iodide (27 g.) in an oil-bath at 140° for 48 hours in a closed soda-water bottle. The neutral reaction product was worked up in the usual manner and 2:2-dimethylcyclobutane-1:1:3:3-tetracarboxylic acid and norpinic acid were isolated and purified by following the method described in the foregoing experiment (the tetracarboxylic acid, m.p. 199°). (Found: C, 46.0; H, 4.8. $C_{10}H_{12}O_8$ requires C, 46.1; H, 4.6 per cent), and norpinic acid, m.p. 145-46° (softening at 136°).

(Found: C, 56.1; H, 7.2. $C_8H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 55.8; H, 6.9 per cent).

The melting point of the norpinic acid and the tetracarboxylic acid prepared as above remained undepressed on admixture with the corresponding samples prepared according to the method of Kerr (*loc. cit.*).

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